

ISic2946

Dedication to Artemis

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

volcanic lava stone

Object

block

Editor

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Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Hybla Gereatis

Place of origin (modern)

Paternò

Provenance

(re)discovered in 19th century in the garden of the (ex) convent of the Cappuccini, Paternò , although already known to 18th century authors

Coordinates

37.562836, 14.893780

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Paterno, Museo Civico Gaetano Savasta

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 22 cm

Width 78 cm

Depth 24 cm

Layout

Three lines of large Greek letters, approximately centred, on the wide face of the block

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Large, wide, simple letters, alpha with straight bar, omicron circular and very slightly smaller than other letters and mid-line.

Letter heights:

Line 1-3: 40-50 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. Επὶ Διουσίῳ ἰ[ερέως]
2. Φιλοκράτης καὶ Ξ[ένων]
3. Ἀρτέμιτι εὐ[χην]

Apparatus

Text of Manganaro 1965

Translation

In the priesthood of Dionysios. Philokrates and Xenon(?), (made) a vow to Artemis

Commentary

Classified as a fake by Kaibel, without autopsy, both Orsi and Manganaro's autopsy confirms the text as genuine

Digital identifiers:

TM 644855

Bibliography

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